

A relationship between p53 and Braf in mammalian cells.

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We measured total transcription in the primary tumor from mice with tumors arising from p53 null status or from genetically engineered mice whose tumors contain a dominant negative p53 mutation to discover cancer cell dependencies associated with p53 status. When comparing total transcription, the Braf transforming kinase encoded by BRAF was among those genes whose expression whose most tightly regulated between cells with p53 KO (knock-out) and mutant p53 genetic status. Braf functioned through interactions with the mitogen-activated protein kinase MAPK8, oncogene ETV3 and the T-complex homeobox Tcf112. BRAF thus appears to be an oncogenic cancer cell dependency in p53-deficient contexts.

Citations

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